

Derivation of the Euler–Lagrange System for Weak-Constraint 4D-Var Data Assimilation of Simulated Wildfire Smoke $PM_{2.5}$ into an Eulerian Transport Model

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June 2021

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of a Master of Science in Mathematical Sciences at AIMS Rwanda

AIMS

African Institute for
Mathematical Sciences
RWANDA

Abstract

The need to quantify smoke concentration over a large area is vital in forecasting air quality. The pollutant of principle concern in smoke is fine particulate matter with diameters 2.5 micrometers and smaller ($PM_{2.5}$) because it can enter lungs and blood streams causing respiratory complications and other diseases and it also absorbs radiations causing warming of the atmosphere thus climate change. Complex mesoscale models are used to accurately explain the dynamics and reactions of $PM_{2.5}$, but these models contain unknown inputs that can be identified using data assimilation. In this study, the weak constraint four-dimensional variational data assimilation (4DVAR) method one of the most comprehensive variational data assimilation techniques is used to assimilate $PM_{2.5}$ data into the one dimensional Eulerian model representing the dynamics and reactions of $PM_{2.5}$. Here we minimize an approximate cost function that gives the Euler Lagrange systems which are then solved for optimal estimates of $PM_{2.5}$ concentration and other model parameters.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Over the last decade, climate change monitoring has become a fundamental activity due to the different effects of climate change such as global warming, increase in sea level and ocean temperatures, and intense droughts that threaten the growth of crops and so on. This has led to the development of studies of the different factors leading to these changes. Atmospheric particulate is one of the major causes of climate change. These particulate emissions to the atmosphere are generated by both natural processes such as volcanic eruptions, and wildfires, and human activities such as quarrying, burning of fossil fuels, agricultural practices, and many others (Benedetti et al., 2009).

According to Ito and Penner (2004), biomass burning, both natural for example wildfires and anthropogenic such as burning for agricultural practices, fuelwood for cooking and heating, to mention, but a few, is a major source of global atmospheric gaseous and particulate emissions (smoke), accounting for approximately 34–38 % and 40% of global carbonaceous aerosol (suspension of fine particles in the air) and black carbon loadings, respectively. Because of their significant radiative effects and climate consequences, aerosol emissions from biomass burning are of particular concern around the world. Smoke particles generated by biomass combustion have a direct effect on air quality, weather, and climate. $PM_{2.5}$, or small particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less, is a major concern in smoke because it can reach the lungs and bloodstream, causing health issues like respiratory complications and heart disease (Levine, 1998).

Smoke transport, once considered solely a local issue, is now recognized as a complex issue influenced by regional, hemispheric, and even global factors. Despite the fact that domestic sources are the primary causes of much of a given country's air quality issues, countries are both sources and receivers of contaminants transported over long distances. Pollutants migrate not only from country to country but also among continents (Council et al., 2010). These contaminants cause public health problems, reduced visibility, cause damage to agricultural and natural plants, decreased domestic and wild animal viability, and damage to infrastructure (Steffen et al., 2016).

Long-range transport of smoke from foreign sources is thus receiving more attention in both the scientific literature and the popular press. Organizations in charge of ensuring that air quality standards are met are increasingly concerned, making the stakeholders have various advanced viewpoints on how localities should address the impact of international pollutant transport in air quality planning (Bertschi and Jaffe, 2005; Council et al., 2010). The need to quantify the concentration of the distant smoke pollutants necessitates the use of complex mesoscale models to accurately explain the processes and dynamics and to adequately integrate chemistry and emissions. For decades, the two components of the related systems, atmospheric physics/dynamics with the largest sub-class of numerical weather prediction models (NWP) and atmospheric chemistry models known as chemistry transport models (CTM), have been developing separately

for historical and practical purposes. However, the basic features and consistency of the evaluation and forecasting of both the condition and composition of the atmosphere calls for Data Assimilation, a process by which observations of a system are incorporated into the model state of a numerical model of that system (Ghil et al., 1981).

Assimilation of observations into numerical models has become a crucial modeling aspect that has led to the development of numerous schemes. These Data Assimilation schemes have developed into extremely complex systems over time, such as the four-dimensional variational method (4DVAR) at the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which is a special case of a generalized least squares problem (Talagrand, 1997). This scheme uses a linearized forecast model to ensure that the observations are given dynamically as well as statistically likely responses in the analysis and can handle a wide range of meteorological data. One of the two approaches to 4DVAR is the weak constraint approach which was used for this study. Weak constraint 4DVAR assumes errors in the model's external forcing, its initial and boundary conditions and hence making the dynamical problem nonlinear even though the model is linear. This approach results into a coupled E-L system of equations hence employing the representer method (Eknes and Evensen, 1997). The representer method is used because of its ability to completely decouple the Euler Lagrange system of equations and the solution is obtained in a finite-dimensional space spanned by the representers, one for each measurement (Van Leeuwen and Evensen, 1996).

1.2 Problem statement

We plan to simulate the long-range regional transport of smoke in one dimension by estimating the concentrations of fine particulate matter with diameters 2.5 micrometers and smaller ($PM_{2.5}$) in the near surface with a one dimensional transport model on an Eulerian grid given by;

$$q_t(x, t) + \nabla \cdot u(x, t)q(x, t) - \nabla \cdot (K \cdot \nabla q(x, t)) + cq(x, t) = Q(x, t), \quad (1.2.1)$$

where $q(x, t)$ is the concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ in (μgm^{-3}), $q^0(x, t)$ is the initial concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ in (μgm^{-3}), $Q(x, t)$ is the source term which denotes the rate of mass influx per unit volume per unit time into the smoke plume ($kgm^{-3}s^{-1}$), $u(x, t)$ represents dispersion by ambient wind in (ms^{-1}), K is a one dimensional diffusivity constant representing turbulent diffusion in (m^2s^{-1}) and c is the decay coefficient of the fall out due to rain or temperature in (Bq).

1.3 Aim and objectives

The main aim of this project is to simulate $PM_{2.5}$ data into the Eulerian transport model using weak constraint 4DVAR with representers and estimate the errors.

The specific objectives are: to derive Euler Lagrange systems of equations when optimizing for $q(x, t)$, $Q(x, t)$, $u(x, t)$, K , and c and decoupling these systems.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Overview of long-range regional transport of smoke

Wang et al. (2006) clearly express the role smoke plays in human health and climate change stating that it [smoke] affects the air quality and climate due to an increase in the concentrations of particulate matter and greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. Smoke which was once a purely local issue was found by Locatelli et al. (2015) to be an international pollutant of great concern by the air quality management stakeholders who came up with ways on how governments should mitigate the transport of these pollutants to and from their countries. For these to be successful, a quantitative understanding of the magnitudes and dynamics of the flows was needed. Similar research was done by Vijayakumar et al. (2016) who also gave the importance of monitoring the long-range transport of smoke and that the key issue in this is predicting the magnitude and location of smoke effects. Based on these research findings came my zeal to study smoke transport, and more specifically focusing on $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations. However, the underlying objective is how this can be done!

Additional findings by Locatelli et al. (2015) suggested the need to quantify the concentration of distant $PM_{2.5}$ using complex mesoscale models to accurately explain the processes and dynamics, as well as to adequately integrate chemistry and emissions. As a result, many experts and academics in different regions have conducted extensive research on $PM_{2.5}$ concentration prediction using both general circulation models (GCMs) with the biggest subset being NWP models that simulate atmospheric dynamics and CTMs which simulate atmospheric chemistry, for practical purposes. Many CTMs have been employed in estimating both ground and atmospheric concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$, for example, Zhou et al. (2018) used the WRF-Chem to reproduce $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations although it overpredicted wind velocity and concentrations in certain areas, the GEOS-Chem global chemical transport model was developed by Van Donkelaar et al. (2010) to estimate surface $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations. Besides the CTMs, most studies on long-range simulation of $PM_{2.5}$ have embarked on using NWP models which are governed by a set of time-dependent partial differential equations corresponding to certain conservation laws of physics for example conservation of mass, momentum, transport equations, and on as presented by Ghil et al. (1981). However, their research still suggested that for better estimation of $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations, the models could be used alongside putting chemical reactions into consideration. In their conclusive remarks, they suggested that despite the recent advancements in all these models, they still exhibit errors that need to be reduced and DA was proposed since it provides the means to produce suitable state estimates as it combines models and actual observations.

2.2 Overview of weak constraint 4D-Var DA technique

Data assimilation as presented by Xiao and Friedrichs (2014), is an important technique that has been widely used in atmospheric research as it evolved from the area's rapid theoretical expansion and the desire to translate it into practical applications. They referred to it as a technique

that combines observation of atmospheric conditions with the system's underlying dynamical principles to produce the best estimate of the system's state where the model's uncertainties are reduced than that which could be obtained when using the data and model separately. [Ide et al. \(1997\)](#), argued that the establishment of a global atmospheric data network that could provide the necessary measurements allowed the use of data assimilation techniques since they involve the systematic use of these measurements to constraint a mathematical model. Data assimilation (DA) therefore, provided a tool for using these findings to boost the operational models' forecasting abilities. There are numerous DA techniques available, each with its own set of limitations.

According to [Wang et al. \(2000\)](#), the development of DA methodology has mainly experienced three stages with the first being the simple analysis methods which were the earliest bases of data assimilation and were mostly used in the 1950s before the era of computers. Statistical considerations were introduced into the atmospheric data assimilation in the 1960s and 1970s and some forms of optimum interpolation were used to assimilate observations into forecast models based on these considerations. The last stage, which is being used to date, comprises sequential and variational DA techniques as grouped by [Talagrand \(1997\)](#). Across several studies, [Evensen \(2002\)](#) stated that sequential DA methods which do not require additional features in the modeling process have proven useful for many atmospheric applications. Some of these methods include the Kalman filter (KF) for linear dynamics and the extended Kalman filter (EKF) for nonlinear dynamics, and to improve the efficiency of the traditional EKF, another method called the ensemble Kalman filter (EnKF) was developed. The 4DVAR and 3DVAR algorithms are the two main variational DA methods that tend to combine the observations and numerical models in an optimal way to give the best possible estimate of the initial model state by minimizing the cost function that measures the weighted sum of square errors. When the time-dependent dimension is taken out, 4DVAR becomes 3DVAR making the former a better scheme for dynamical systems than the latter. It was also revealed that although variational schemes are rarely used, they are found to be more successful than other algorithms ([Ide et al., 1997](#)).

Particularly, the 4DVAR data assimilation method that seeks to minimize the cost function defined as the weighted sum of squared deviation between the model and the observations became operational in 1997 [Eknes and Evensen \(1997\)](#). This method corrects the model in a four-dimensional domain, that is, the three spatial dimensions and the time dimension using the model dynamics as a constraint, either strong or weak. The two approaches to this method are the weak and strong constraints 4DVAR and these differ in such a way that the strong constraints 4DVAR assume a perfect model implying the error is confined in the initial model state while the weak constraints assume errors in the observations, model external forcing, initial and boundary conditions relaxing the perfect model assumption as discussed by [Gustafsson et al. \(2012\)](#).

According to [Zupanski \(1997\)](#), the weak constraints 4DVAR has always yielded accurate results because it includes all the information that may be lost by the strong constraints method and its also capable of altering the dynamics of a given model hence fitting the observations. The effectiveness of weak constraints 4DVAR algorithm in correcting and estimating the model error in 4DVAR for long-range assimilation windows was the motivation for its use in this study as it assimilates observations through the minimization of a least-squares cost function which is a function of the error between the model and the measurements, seeking for an optimal solution.

To solve the dynamic problem, coupled Euler Lagrange equations are obtained from the minimized problem for which a convergent iteration can then be defined. The improved estimates of the poorly known parameters can be calculated by solving the problem for each of the linear iterates using the representer which expresses the problem as the sum of a first guess and a finite linear combination of representer functions. It formulates the problem in such a way that the solution procedure involves only covariance multiplications, and not their inverses, with variables defined in the state and the observations spaces. The representer method is adopted for solving weak constraints 4DVAR problems because of its ability to decouple the Euler Lagrange system hence giving the minimum solution as portrayed by [Bennett \(1992\)](#).

3. Weak Constraint 4DVAR

This chapter discusses the implementation of weak constraint 4DVAR with representers to assimilate wind fields, emission, and $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations data directly into the transport model (1.2.1) as it allows to alter the dynamics of the model for better results. Using this method involved derivation of Euler Lagrange equations when optimizing the state variable $q(x, t)$ as well as the input that is; $Q(x, t)$, $u(x, t)$, K , and c and then using the representer method to decouple the E-L systems making the scheme computationally feasible.

3.1 The model

In this study, the model used for estimating $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations $q(x, t)$ is an Eulerian one dimensional transport model given as below;

$$\begin{cases} q_t(x, t) + u_x(x, t)q(x, t) + u(x, t)q_x(x, t) - Kq_{xx}(x, t) + cq(x, t) = Q(x, t) \\ q(x, 0) = q^0(x) \quad x \in \Omega, \quad t \in [0, T] \end{cases} \quad (3.1.1)$$

where $q = q(x, t)$ is the concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ in (μgm^{-3}), $q^0(x, t)$ is the initial concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ in (μgm^{-3}), $Q = Q(x, t)$ is the source term which denotes the rate of mass influx per unit volume per unit time into the smoke plume ($kgm^{-3}s^{-1}$), $u = u(x, t)$ represents dispersion by ambient wind in (ms^{-1}), K is a one dimensional diffusivity constant representing turbulent diffusion in (m^2s^{-1}) and c is the decay coefficient of the fall out due to rain or temperature in (Bq) and since this is a one dimensional model.

If inputs $u(x, t)$, K , c and $Q(x, t)$ are represented accurately, equation (3.1.1) contains all of the factors that contribute to smoke behavior. This includes, the emission source, plume rise, transport and dispersion by ambient wind, as well as chemical reactions in the smoke.

3.2 Data

The data assumes a finite number of observations collected within a temporal domain $0 \leq t \leq T$ and a spatial domain $0 \leq x \leq L$. Following [Furtado et al. \(2010\)](#), these observations are imperfect point measurements of the independent variable $\beta(x, t)$ collected at M points in space at time (x_m, t_m) and these are given by;

$$d_m = H_\beta \beta(x_m, t_m) + \epsilon_m \quad 1 \leq m \leq M$$

where H_β is the observation operator that transforms the unknown $\beta(x, t)$ into observation equivalents and ϵ_m is the measurement error.

3.3 The cost function

According to Ngodock et al. (2017), the weak constraint 4DVAR scheme is said to assume errors in the governing equations due to parametrization, unresolved processes, and the forcing. The first step was therefore to add error terms to the model, observations, and initial conditions as presented in equations (3.3.1) and (3.3.2) below:

$$\begin{cases} q_t(x, t) + u_x(x, t)q(x, t) + u(x, t)q_x(x, t) - Kq_{xx}(x, t) + cq(x, t) = Q(x, t) + f(x, t) \\ q(x, 0) = q^0(x) + i(x) \quad x \in \Omega, \quad t \in [0, T] \end{cases} \quad (3.3.1)$$

where $f(x, t)$ and $i(x)$ are errors in the dynamics and initial condition respectively. The boundary conditions were assumed to be exact periodic with no errors that is $q(0, t) = q(L, t)$.

In addition, initial estimates of; the emission $Q(x, t)$ along with it's data at points (x_Q, t_Q) , the dispersion by ambient wind $u(x, t)$ along with it's data at points (x_u, t_u) , the diffusivity constant K , decay constant c and a limited number of concentration data at points (x_q, t_q) were assumed to be present with uncertainties $E(x, t)$, ϵ_Q , $E_u(x, t)$, ϵ_u , Γ , γ and ϵ_q associated with them respectively. These were presented as below:

$$\begin{aligned} Q(x, t) &= Q^0(x, t) + E(x, t) \\ u(x, t) &= u^0(x, t) + E_u(x, t) \\ dq &= H_q q(x_q, t_q) + \epsilon_q \\ dQ &= H_Q Q(x_Q, t_Q) + \epsilon_Q \\ du &= H_u u(x_u, t_u) + \epsilon_u \\ K &= K^0 + \Gamma \\ c &= c^0 + \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (3.3.2)$$

where H_* is an observation operator that transforms either $Q(x, t)$, $u(x, t)$ or $q(x, t)$ into observation equivalents.

The errors $f(x, t)$, $E(x, t)$, $E_u(x, t)$, $i(x)$, ϵ_q , ϵ_Q , ϵ_u , Γ , and γ were assumed to be normally distributed each with a covariance C_f , C_E , C_{E_u} , C_i , C_{ϵ_q} , C_{ϵ_Q} , C_{ϵ_u} , C_Γ and C_γ with corresponding inverse covariances given as W_f , W_E , W_{E_u} , W_i , W_{ϵ_q} , W_{ϵ_Q} , W_{ϵ_u} , W_Γ and W_γ respectively.

Since the core reason for the implementation of the weak constraint 4DVAR is to give the best estimates of the model, this is achieved by minimizing the cost function (the weighted sum of squared errors) in a least-squares sense to produce the maximum likelihood estimate (Bennett, 1992). The cost function \mathcal{J} below was therefore formed as a sum of squared errors as shown

below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{J} = & W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} f(x, t)^2 dx dt + W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} E(x, t)^2 dx dt + W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} E_u(x, t)^2 dx dt \\
& + W_i \int_{\Omega} i(x)^2 dx + W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M (\epsilon_q)_m^2 + W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J (\epsilon_Q)_j^2 \\
& + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N (\epsilon_u)_n^2 + W_{\Gamma} \Gamma^2 + W_{\gamma} \gamma^2
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.3}$$

Rewriting the above equation (3.3.3) while substituting for $f(x, t)$, $i(x)$, and ϵ_q , it becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{J} = & W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} + cq - Q \right]^2 dx dt \\
& + W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[Q(x, t) - Q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt + W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[u(x, t) - u^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt \\
& + W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[q(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx + W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q q(x_m, t_m) \right]^2 \\
& + W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q Q(x_j, t_j) \right]^2 + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u u(x_n, t_n) \right]^2 \\
& + W_{\Gamma} (K - K^0)^2 + W_{\gamma} (c - c^0)^2
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.4}$$

3.4 Derivation of Euler Lagrange systems separately

This section represents the derivation of E-L systems of equations when optimizing for $q(x, t)$, $Q(x, t)$, $u(x, t)$, K , and c separately and then simultaneously which were then either decoupled using the representer method or solved by substitution.

3.4.1 Optimizing for the state variable $q(x, t)$. This involved deriving an E-L system of equations when optimizing for the concentration of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ which was done by minimizing the functional (3.3.4) in a least square sense with respect to $q(x, t)$. The E-L system formed was decoupled using the representer method to produce the maximum likelihood estimate. The calculus of variations techniques was employed in deriving the system.

Bennett (2005) presented that for whatever choice $f(x, t)$ and $i(x)$, there is a unique solution for $q(x, t)$. However, not all points in space have observations making the error fields $f(x, t)$ and $E(x, t)$ undetermined and the data error ϵ_q unknown. Therefore the field $\hat{q} = \hat{q}(x, t)$ that corresponds to the smallest values of the errors; $f(x, t)$, $i(x)$, and ϵ_q in a weighted least square sense is said to be the local extremum of the functional \mathcal{J} . To find the local extremum of \mathcal{J} , the calculus of variation is used and since \mathcal{J} is non-negative and quadratic in q , the local extremum must be the global minimum (**Gottlieb and Orszag, 1977**). If \hat{q} is the local extremum, then using Taylor series expansion of \mathcal{J} around the point \hat{q} we have that:

$$\mathcal{J}[\hat{q} + \delta q] = \mathcal{J}[\hat{q}] + \nabla \mathcal{J}(q) \delta q + \mathcal{O}(\delta q)^2$$

For some small quantity $\delta q = \delta q(x, t)$ the approximation below is obtained:

$$\mathcal{J}[\hat{q} + \delta q] - \mathcal{J}[\hat{q}] \approx \nabla \mathcal{J}(q) \delta q$$

The first variation for functional \mathcal{J} is then given as:

$$\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}[\hat{q} + \delta q] - \mathcal{J}[\hat{q}]$$

The explicit form for the functional (3.3.4) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}[\hat{q}] = & W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \hat{q} + u \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} + c \hat{q} - Q \right]^2 dx dt \\ & + W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[Q(x, t) - Q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt + W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[u(x, t) - u^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt \\ & + W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx + W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right]^2 \\ & + W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q Q(x_j, t_j) \right]^2 + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u u(x_n, t_n) \right]^2 \\ & + W_{\Gamma} (K - K^0)^2 + W_{\gamma} (c - c^0)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.1)$$

The expression for $\mathcal{J}[\hat{q} + \delta q]$ is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}[\hat{q} + \delta q] = & W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial t} + \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) (\hat{q} + \delta q) + u \left(\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} \right) - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - K \frac{\partial^2 \delta q}{\partial x^2} - Q \right]^2 \\ & \times dx dt + W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[Q(x, t) - Q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt \\ & + W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[u(x, t) - u^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx dt \\ & + W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) + \delta q(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right]^2 dx \\ & + W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) - H_q \delta q(x_m, t_m) \right]^2 + W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q Q(x_j, t_j) \right]^2 \\ & + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u u(x_n, t_n) \right]^2 + W_{\Gamma} (K - K^0)^2 + W_{\gamma} (c - c^0)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.2)$$

Subtracting equation (3.4.1) from (3.4.2) and using the knowledge of difference of squares and

neglecting variations of second-order, yielded:

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\mathcal{J} = & 2W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right) \hat{q} + u \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - Q \right] \\
& \times \left[\frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial t} + \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right) \delta q + u \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \delta q}{\partial x^2} \right] dx dt \\
& + 2W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right] \delta q dx \\
& - 2W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta q
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.3}$$

Let $\lambda = \lambda(x, t) \equiv W_f \left[\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right) \hat{q} + u \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - Q \right]$. Since equation (3.4.3) is in terms of δq , $\frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial t}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 \delta q}{\partial x^2}$, it calls for integration by parts to make the equation to be in terms of δq only as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\mathcal{J} = & 2 \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda(x, t) \delta q \right]_0^T dx - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} \delta q dx dt + 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda(x, t) \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right) \delta q dx dt \\
& + 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda(x, t) u(x, t) \delta q \right]_0^L - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} u(x, t) \right] \delta q dx dt \\
& - 2K \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \delta q \right]_0^L dt + 2K \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} \right]_0^L dt - 2K \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} \delta q dx dt \\
& + 2W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right] \delta q dx - 2W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta q(x_m, t_m)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.4}$$

The filtering property of the Dirac delta is then employed to the equation 3.4.4 above to eliminate $\delta(x_m, t_m)$ as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta q(x_m, t_m) = & \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] \\
& \times H_q^T \delta(x_m - x) \delta(t_m - t) \delta q dx dt
\end{aligned}$$

Having expressed $\delta\mathcal{J}$ in terms of δq only and taking note that boundary terms are equal and opposite due to the periodic boundary condition, following Bennett (2005) \hat{q} is the local extremum of \mathcal{J} iff $\delta\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta q)^2$. Therefore the local minimum occurs iff the coefficients of $\delta q(x, t)$, $\delta q(x, 0)$, $\delta q(x, T)$, $\delta q(0, t)$ and $\delta q(L, t)$ in equation (3.4.4) vanish giving the system of Euler- Lagrange

system of equations below:

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - K \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} - (u(x, t) - c) \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \\ \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \left(c + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) \hat{q} + u(x, t) \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} = Q(x, t) + C_f \lambda(x, t) \\ \hat{q}(x, 0) = q^0(x, t) + C_i \lambda(x, 0) \\ \lambda(x, T) = 0 \\ \lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t) \\ \hat{q}(0, t) = \hat{q}(L, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.5)$$

Solving the E-L system using the representer method

Re ordering the Euler- Lagrange system of equations gives both the backward in time and forward in time systems as show in (3.4.6) and (3.4.7) respectively.

$$(B) \begin{cases} -\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - K \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} - (u(x, t) - c) \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \\ \lambda(x, T) = 0 \\ \lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.6)$$

$$(F) \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \hat{q} + (u(x, t) - c) \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} = Q(x, t) + C_f \lambda(x, t) \\ \hat{q}(x, 0) = q^0(x, t) + C_i \lambda(x, 0) \\ \hat{q}(0, t) = \hat{q}(L, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.7)$$

From equation (3.4.7), best estimates for errors $f(x, t)$ and $i(x, 0)$ are given by:

$$\hat{f}(x, t) = C_f \lambda(x, t) \text{ and } \hat{i}(x, 0) = C_i \lambda(x, 0).$$

The backward or adjoint and forward problems in (3.4.6) and (3.4.7) respectively can be solved using the representer method which decouples the E-L equations (Furtado et al., 2010). This method expresses the optimal solution as the sum of a first guess (prior estimate) q_F and a finite linear combination of representer functions $r_m(x, t)$, one per datum for $1 \leq m \leq M$ and each having an adjoint $\alpha_m(x, t)$ as shown below:

$$\hat{q} = q_F(x, t) + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m r_m(x, t) \quad (3.4.8)$$

where β_m are the unknown representer coefficients. The first guess q_F is the solution to the model in (3.1.1) without errors as shown below:

$$(F) \begin{cases} \frac{\partial q_F}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q_F + (u(x, t) - c) \frac{\partial q_F}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q_F}{\partial x^2} = Q(x, t) \\ q_F(x, 0) = q^0(x, t) \\ q_F(0, t) = q_F(L, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.9)$$

The representer function and adjoint associated with the m th observation are the solutions to the backward and forward systems below:

$$(B_m) \begin{cases} -\frac{\partial \alpha_m}{\partial t} - K \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_m}{\partial x^2} - (u(x, t) - c) \frac{\partial \alpha_m}{\partial x} = H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \\ \alpha_m(x, T) = 0 \\ \alpha_m(L, t) = \alpha_m(0, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.10)$$

$$(F_m) \begin{cases} \frac{\partial r_m}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} r_m + (u - c) \frac{\partial r_m}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 r_m}{\partial x^2} = C_f \alpha_m(x, t) \\ r_m(x, 0) = C_i \alpha_m(x, 0) \\ r_m(0, t) = r_m(L, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.11)$$

When manipulating e(3.4.10), it was observed that $\beta_m = \hat{\beta}_m = -W_{\epsilon_q} [H_m \hat{q}_m - d_m]$ and substituting for \hat{q}_m , the representer coefficients became:

$$\hat{\beta}_m = -W_{\epsilon_q} \left\{ H_m q_F(x_m, t_m) + H_m \sum_{l=1}^M \hat{\beta}_l r_l(x_m, t_m) - d_m \right\}$$

Hence

$$\sum_{l=1}^M (H_m r_l(x_m, t_m) + C_{\epsilon_q} \delta_{lm}) \hat{\beta}_l = h_m \quad (3.4.12)$$

where $h_m = d_m - H_m q_F(x_m, t_m)$ and δ_{lm} is the Kronecker delta. The matrix notation for the M equations (3.4.12) above is given as:

$$(\mathbf{R} + C_{\epsilon_q} \mathbf{I}) \hat{\beta} = \mathbf{h} = \mathbf{d}_q - \mathbf{H}_q \mathbf{q}_F \quad (3.4.13)$$

where $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, $C_{\epsilon_q} \mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, $\hat{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{d}_q - \mathbf{H}_q \mathbf{q}_F \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$

To find the M representer coefficients, we make $\hat{\beta}$ the subject in (3.4.13) and substitute for them in (3.4.8) to get the explicit solution for \hat{q} as shown below:

$$\hat{q}(x, t) = q_F(x, t) + (\mathbf{d}_q - \mathbf{H}_q \mathbf{q}_F)^T (\mathbf{R} + C_{\epsilon_q} \mathbf{I})^{-1} r(x, t) \quad (3.4.14)$$

3.4.2 Optimizing for the source term. In this subsection, the E-L system of equations was derived when optimizing for $Q(x, t)$. To obtain the optimal estimate for the source term, the cost function (3.3.4) was minimized with respect to $Q = Q(x, t)$ with steps similar to those when optimizing with respect to $q(x, t)$. the calculus of variations technique was also used in a similar way to minimise equation (3.3.4) with. For this case the local extremum of the functional was assumed to be $\hat{Q} = \hat{Q}(x, t)$ and therefore the first variation of the \mathcal{J} given by

$\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}[\hat{Q} + \delta Q] + \mathcal{J}[\hat{Q}]$ was obtained as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{J} = & -2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda(x, t) \delta Q dx dt + 2W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{Q} - Q^0(x, t) \right] \delta Q dx dt \\ & - 2W_{\epsilon_Q} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \delta Q dx dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.15)$$

where $\lambda(x, t) = W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{Q}(x, t) \right]$. The filtering property of the Dirac delta was then employed to equation (3.4.15) to eliminate $\delta(x_j, t_j)$;

$$\sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \delta Q(x_j, t_j) \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T = \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \delta Q dx dt \quad (3.4.16)$$

Having expressed $\delta \mathcal{J}$ in terms of δQ , and as argued that $\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta Q)^2$, for \hat{Q} to be the local extremum of \mathcal{J} , the coefficients of $\delta Q(x, t)$ must vanish giving the E-L equations below;

$$\begin{cases} \hat{Q}(x, t) = Q^0(x, t) + C_E \lambda(x, t) + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \\ \lambda(x, t) = W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{Q}(x, t) \right] \end{cases} \quad (3.4.17)$$

Solving the E-L system

The optimal estimate $\hat{Q}(x, t)$ could then be obtained from the E-L equations by substituting for $\lambda(x, t)$ in the equation for \hat{Q} above as shown below:

$$\hat{Q}(x, t) = \begin{cases} Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{Q}(x, t) \right]; & \text{for } x \neq x_j \\ Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{Q}(x, t) \right] \\ + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} ((d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j)); & \text{for } x = x_j \end{cases} \quad (3.4.18)$$

Simplifying equation (3.4.18) gives;

$$\hat{Q}(x, t) = \begin{cases} A^{-1} \left\{ Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \right] \right\}; & \text{for } x \neq x_j \\ B^{-1} \left\{ Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \right] + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} d_Q \right\}; & \text{for } x = x_j \end{cases} \quad (3.4.19)$$

where $A = I + C_E W_f$, $B = I + C_E W_f + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} H_Q$ and I is an identity matrix

3.4.3 Optimizing for the diffusivity constant. In this sub-section, the E-L system was derived by minimizing the cost function (3.3.4) with respect to K . Similarly the calculus of variations technique was employed as earlier to minimize the functional in a least square sense hose the local extremum was assumed to be \hat{K} hence giving the first variation $\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}[\hat{K} + \delta K] - \mathcal{J}[\hat{K}]$

as below:

$$\delta\mathcal{J} = -2W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} \delta K dx dt + 2W_{\Gamma} (\hat{K} - K^0) \delta K \quad (3.4.20)$$

let $\lambda(x, t) = W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt$. As argued by Bennett (2005) that $\delta\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta K)^2$, for \hat{K} to be a local extremum of \mathcal{J} then coefficients of δK in equation (3.4.20) must go to zero giving the E-L system below;

$$\begin{cases} \hat{K} = K^0 + C_{\Gamma} \lambda(x, t) \\ \lambda(x, t) = W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt \end{cases} \quad (3.4.21)$$

Solving the E-L system

The optimal estimate \hat{K} was obtained by substituting for λ in the equation for \hat{K} as shown below

$$\hat{K} = K^0 + C_{\Gamma} W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt \quad (3.4.22)$$

Making \hat{K} the subject in equation (3.4.22) above yields:

$$\hat{K} = \frac{K^0 + C_{\Gamma} W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt}{1 + C_{\Gamma} W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} * \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt} \quad (3.4.23)$$

3.4.4 Optimizing for the decay coefficient. For this case, the cost function was minimized in the least square sense with respect to c using the calculus of variations technique seen earlier to obtain the maximum likelihood estimate for the decay coefficient. The local extremum for the functional (3.3.4) was assumed to be \hat{c} and hence the first variation $\delta\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}[\hat{c} + \delta c] - \mathcal{J}[\hat{c}]$ was obtained as;

$$\delta\mathcal{J} = -2W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - \hat{c} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \delta c dx dt + 2W_{\Gamma} (\hat{c} - c^0) \delta c \quad (3.4.24)$$

let $\lambda(x, t) = W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - \hat{c} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} dx dt$. Basing on the argument that $\delta\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta c)^2$, for \hat{c} to be a local extremum of \mathcal{J} then coefficients of δc in equation (3.4.24) must vanish giving the E-L system of equations as;

$$\begin{cases} \hat{c} = c^0 + C_{\gamma} \lambda(x, t) \\ \lambda(x, t) W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - \hat{c} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] * \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \delta c dx dt \end{cases} \quad (3.4.25)$$

Solving the E-L system

Substituting for $\lambda(x, t)$ in the equation for \hat{c} and then making \hat{c} the subject gives:

$$\hat{c} = \frac{c^0 + C_\gamma W_f \int_0^T \int_\Omega \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - Q \right] \times \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} dx dt}{1 + C_\gamma W_f \int_0^T \int_\Omega \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \times \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} dx dt} \quad (3.4.26)$$

3.4.5 Optimizing for the dispersion by ambient wind. For this case the E-L system of equations was derived when optimizing for the dispersion by ambient wind and this was done by minimizing the cost function (3.3.4) in the least square sense with respect to $u(x, t)$ to obtain the maximum likelihood estimate. The calculus of variations method was used following similar steps as those for obtaining equation (3.4.3) above with $\hat{u} = \hat{u}(x, t)$ as the local extremum to the functional (3.3.4) above giving $\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}[\hat{u} + \delta u] - \mathcal{J}[\hat{u}]$ as below;

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{J} = & 2 \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial \delta u}{\partial x} q(x, t) dx dt + 2 \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) q_x \delta u dx dt \\ & + 2W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_\Omega \left[\hat{u}(x, t) - u^0(x, t) \right] \delta u dx dt - 2W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta u \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.27)$$

where $\lambda(x, t) \equiv W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} q + \hat{u} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q(x, t) \right]$. Unlike equation (3.4.15) whose terms were only in δQ , for (3.4.27) the terms are both in δu and $\frac{\partial \delta u}{\partial x}$ hence the need for integrating the equation by parts and also using the filtering property of the Dirac delta functions to express $\delta \mathcal{J}$ in terms of δu only as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{J} = & 2 \int_0^T \lambda(L, t) q(L, t) \delta u(L, t) dt - 2 \int_0^T \lambda(0, t) q(0, t) \delta u(0, t) dt \\ & - 2 \int_0^T \int_\Omega \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} q(x, t) \delta u dx dt + 2W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_\Omega \left[\hat{u} - u^0(x, t) \right] \delta u dx dt \\ & - 2W_{\epsilon_u} \int_0^T \int_\Omega \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \delta u dx dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.28)$$

The boundary terms are equal and opposite, due to the periodic boundary condition. Having expressed $\delta \mathcal{J}$ entirely in terms of δu and as argued earlier that $\delta \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta u)^2$, this implies that \hat{u} is the extremum of \mathcal{J} provided the coefficients of $\delta u(x, t)$, $\delta u(0, t)$ and $\delta u(L, t)$ vanish hence giving the Euler- Lagrange equations below;

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} q(x, t) = -W_{E_u} [\hat{u}(x, t) - u^0(x, t)] + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \\ \lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t) \\ \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} q + \hat{u} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} = C_f \lambda(x, t) - \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} + c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q(x, t) \\ q(L, t) = q(0, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.29)$$

Solving the E-L system

$$(B) \begin{cases} -\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} q(x, t) = -W_{Eu} [\hat{u}(x, t) - u^0(x, t)] + W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \\ \lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.30)$$

$$(F) \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} q + \hat{u} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} = C_f \lambda(x, t) - \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} + c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q(x, t) \\ q(L, t) = q(0, t) \end{cases} \quad (3.4.31)$$

This is solved using numerical finite difference schemes

let $\lambda_i^k \approx \lambda(x_i, t_k)$, $q_i^k \approx q(x_j, t_k)$, and $\hat{u}_i^k \approx \hat{u}(x_j, t_k)$ for $1 \leq i \leq I$ and $1 \leq k \leq K$

the solution can be obtained from:

$$\frac{\lambda_{i+1}^k - \lambda_i^k}{\Delta x} q_i^k = \begin{cases} -W_{Eu} [\hat{u}_i^k - u^{0k}] \text{ for } x_i \neq x_n \\ -W_{Eu} [\hat{u}_i^k - u^{0k}] + W_{\epsilon_u} [d_u - H_u \hat{u}_i^k] \text{ for } x_i = x_n \end{cases} \quad (3.4.32)$$

$$\frac{\hat{u}_{i+1}^k - \hat{u}_i^k}{\Delta x} q_i^k = - + \frac{q_i^k - q_{i-1}^k}{\Delta x} u_i^k C_f \lambda_i^k - f_i^k \quad (3.4.33)$$

3.5 Derivation of the Euler Lagrange system simultaneously

This section shows the derivation of the E-L system when optimizing for the concentration of $PM_{2.5}$, emission source, ambient dispersion of wind, the decay constant due to rainfall or temperature and the diffusivity constant simultaneously. This was done by minimizing the cost function (3.3.4) in a least square sense with respect to $q(x, t)$, $Q(x, t)$, $u(x, t)$, K and c using the calculus of variations technique as earlier used when optimizing for $q(x, t)$. For this, the local extrema for the functional \mathcal{J} were assumed to be \hat{q} , \hat{Q} , \hat{u} , \hat{K} and \hat{c} respectively. The first variation; $\delta J = J[\hat{q} + \delta q, \hat{Q} + \delta Q, \hat{u} + \delta u, \hat{K} + \delta K, \hat{c} + \delta c] - J[\hat{q}, \hat{Q}, \hat{u}, \hat{K}, \hat{c}]$ was then obtained as

below;

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta \mathcal{J} = & 2W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} \hat{q} + \hat{u} \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - \hat{c} \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} - \hat{Q} \right] \times \\
& \left(\frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} \delta q + \frac{\partial \delta u}{\partial x} \hat{q} + \delta u \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} + \hat{u} \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} - \delta K \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 \delta q}{\partial x^2} - \delta c \hat{q}_x - \hat{c} \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} - \delta Q \right) dx dt \\
& + 2W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{Q} - Q^0(x, t) \right] \delta Q dx dt + 2W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{u} - u^0(x, t) \right] \delta u dx dt \\
& + 2W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right] \delta q dx - 2W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta q - \\
& 2W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta Q - 2W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta u \\
& + 2W_{\Gamma} (\hat{K} - K^0) \delta K + 2W_{\gamma} (\hat{c} - c^0) \delta c
\end{aligned} \tag{3.5.1}$$

let $\lambda = \lambda(x, t) \equiv W_f \left[\hat{q}_t(x, t) + \hat{u}_x \hat{q} + \hat{u} \hat{q}_x - \hat{K} \nabla^2 \hat{q}(x, t) - \hat{c} \nabla \cdot \hat{q}(x, t) - \hat{Q} \right]$. Since equation (3.5.1) is in terms of δq , δu , δQ , δK , δc , $\frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial t}$, $\frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x}$, and $\frac{\partial \delta u}{\partial x}$, integration by parts as well as the filtering property of the Dirac delta functions were employed to make the equation be in terms of δq , δu , δQ , δK , and δc only as shown below;

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\mathcal{J} = & 2 \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda \delta q \right]_0^T dx - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} \delta q dx dt + 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} \delta q dx dt + 2 \int_0^T \left[\lambda \hat{q} \delta u \right]_{\Omega} dt \\
& - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \hat{q} \right] \delta u dx dt + 2 \int_0^T \left[\lambda \hat{u} \delta q \right]_{\Omega} dt - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\lambda \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \hat{u} \right] \delta q dx dt \\
& + 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} \delta u dx dt - 2 \hat{K} \int_0^T \left[\lambda \frac{\partial \delta q}{\partial x} \right]_{\Omega} dt + 2 \hat{K} \int_0^T \left[\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \delta q \right]_{\Omega} dt \\
& - 2 \hat{K} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} \delta q dx dt - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} \delta K dx dt - 2 \hat{c} \int_0^T \left[\lambda \delta q \right]_{\Omega} dt + 2 \hat{c} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \delta q dx dt \\
& - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} \delta c dx dt - 2 \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \lambda \delta Q dx dt + 2 W_E \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{Q} - Q^0(x, t) \right] \delta Q dx dt \\
& + 2 W_{E_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{u} - u^0(x, t) \right] \delta u dx dt + 2 W_i \int_{\Omega} \left[\hat{q}(x, 0) - q^0(x, t) \right] \delta q dx \\
& - 2 W_{\epsilon_q} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \delta q dx dt \\
& - 2 W_{\epsilon_Q} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \delta Q dx dt \\
& - 2 W_{\epsilon_u} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \delta u dx dt \\
& + W_{\Gamma} (\hat{K} - K^0) \delta K + W_{\gamma} (\hat{c} - c^0) \delta c
\end{aligned} \tag{3.5.2}$$

Taking into account that the boundary terms are equal and opposite, due to the periodic boundary condition and the argument made by [Bennett \(2005\)](#) that $\delta\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{O}(\delta q)^2 + \mathcal{O}(\delta Q)^2 + \mathcal{O}(\delta u)^2 + \mathcal{O}(\delta K)^2 + \mathcal{O}(\delta c)^2$, for \hat{q} , \hat{Q} , \hat{u} , \hat{K} and \hat{c} to be local extrema for \mathcal{J} , coefficients of $\delta q(x, t)$, $\delta q(x, 0)$, $\delta q(x, T)$, $\delta q(0, t)$, $\delta q(L, t)$, $\delta u(x, t)$, $\delta u(0, t)$, $\delta u(x, L)$, $\delta Q(x, t)$, $\delta K(x, t)$, and $\delta c(x, t)$ must vanish giving the system of Euler Lagrange equations below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
-\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} - (\hat{u}(x, t) - \hat{c}) \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \\
\frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial t} \hat{q} + \hat{u} \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} - \hat{c} \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial t} = \hat{Q} + C_f \lambda(x, t) \\
\hat{u}(x, t) = u^0(x, t) + C_{E_u} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \hat{q}(x, t) + C_{E_u} W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \\
\hat{Q}(x, t) = Q^0(x, t) + C_E \lambda(x, t) + C_{E_Q} W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \\
\hat{K} = K^0 + C_\Gamma \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} dx dt \\
\hat{c} = c^0 + C_\gamma \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} dx dt \\
\hat{q}(x, 0) = q^0(x, t) + C_i \lambda(x, 0) \\
\lambda(x, T) = 0 \\
\lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t) \\
\hat{q}(L, t) = \hat{q}(0, t)
\end{array} \right. \quad (3.5.3)$$

Solving the E-L system

Re ordering the Euler- Lagrange of equation (3.5.3) gives the backward problem (3.5.4) , forward problem (3.5.5) and the optimal estimates of the parameters as shown below:

$$(B) \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
-\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - \hat{K} \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} - (\hat{u}(x, t) - \hat{c}) \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = W_{\epsilon_q} \sum_{m=1}^M \left[(d_q)_m - H_q \hat{q}(x_m, t_m) \right] H_q^T \delta(x - x_m) \delta(t - t_m) \\
\lambda(x, T) = 0 \\
\lambda(L, t) = \lambda(0, t)
\end{array} \right. \quad (3.5.4)$$

$$(F) \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\hat{q}_t(x, t) + \hat{u}_x(x, t) \hat{q} + \hat{u} \hat{q}_x - \hat{K} \nabla^2 \hat{q}(x, t) - \hat{c} \nabla \cdot \hat{q}(x, t) = \hat{Q} + C_f \lambda(x, t) \\
\hat{q}(x, 0) = q^0(x, t) + C_i \lambda(x, 0) \\
\hat{q}(0, t) = \hat{q}(L, t)
\end{array} \right. \quad (3.5.5)$$

with parameter estimates;

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\hat{u}(x, t) = u^0(x, t) + C_{E_u} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \hat{q}(x, t) + C_{E_u} W_{\epsilon_u} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[(d_u)_n - H_u \hat{u}(x_n, t_n) \right] H_u^T \delta(x - x_n) \delta(t - t_n) \\
\hat{Q}(x, t) = Q^0(x, t) + C_E \lambda(x, t) + C_{E_Q} W_{\epsilon_Q} \sum_{j=1}^J \left[(d_Q)_j - H_Q \hat{Q}(x_j, t_j) \right] H_Q^T \delta(x - x_j) \delta(t - t_j) \\
\hat{K} = K^0 + C_\Gamma \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial^2 \hat{q}}{\partial x^2} dx dt \\
\hat{c} = c^0 + C_\gamma \int_0^T \int_\Omega \lambda(x, t) \frac{\partial \hat{q}}{\partial x} dx dt
\end{array} \right. \quad (3.5.6)$$

4. Pseudo Code for the E-L Systems

4.1 Sample pseudo code for \hat{q}

Basing equations (3.4.8) to (3.4.14) above, the pseudo code for \hat{q} can be represented as below:

1. Start
2. Input covariance matrix C_{ϵ_q} and matrix for the observation operator \mathbf{H}_q
3. Compute q_F by numerical integration of equation (3.4.9)
4. Compute innovation \mathbf{h} according to $\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{d}_q - \mathbf{H}_q \mathbf{q}_F$
5. Compute the adjoint representer $\alpha_m(x, t)$ according to equation(3.4.10)
6. Compute the representer $r_m(x, t)$ for $1 \leq m \leq M$ according to equation(3.4.11)
7. compute $r_m(x_l, t_l)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $l = 1, 2, \dots, m$ that is matrix $\mathbf{R}_{M \times M}$
8. Compute $\mathbf{P} = (\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{C}_{\epsilon_q} \mathbf{I})$
9. Compute the analysis given by the following equation:

$$\hat{q}(x, t) = q_F(x, t) + \mathbf{h}^T \mathbf{P}^{-1} r(x, t)$$
10. Stop

4.2 Sample pseudo code for \hat{Q}

$$\hat{Q}(x, t) = \begin{cases} A^{-1} \left\{ Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \right] \right\}; & \text{for } x \neq x_j \\ B^{-1} \left\{ Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \right] + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} d_Q \right\}; & \text{for } x = x_j \end{cases} \quad (4.2.1)$$

where $A = I + C_E W_f$, $B = I + C_E W_f + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} H_Q$ and I is an identity matrix

The pseudo code for (4.2.1) is as below:

1. Start
2. Define Function $Q^0(x, t)$
3. Define Function $Q(x, t)$

4. Input d_Q , x_m , C_E , W_f , and W_{ϵ_Q}
5. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (L) and number of sub intervals (N) for x
6. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (T) and number of sub intervals (M) for t
7. Calculate A and B
8. Create arrays for t and x using their lower limits, upper limits and number of sub intervals respectively
9. Create an empty array for $\hat{Q}(x, t)$ with dimension $(M+1) \times (N + 1)$
10. Start a for loop as shown below:


```

for  $t = 0$  to  $T$  do
  for  $x = 0$  to  $L$  do
    if  $x \neq x_j$  then
       $\hat{Q}(x, t) = A^{-1} [Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f Q(x, t)]$ 
    else
       $\hat{Q}(x, t) = B^{-1} [Q^0(x, t) + C_E W_f Q(x, t) + C_E W_{\epsilon_Q} d_Q]$ 
    end if
  end for
end for

```
11. Print $\hat{Q}(x, t)$ as the result
12. Stop

The code above was implemented to simulate the emission source as shown in figure 4.1 below. The covariance matrices in (4.2.1) were taken to be equal to one, the initial source term was assumed to be an exponential term since smoke grows/ decays exponentially that is:

$$Q^0(x, t) = c \exp(x - x_j)$$

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} = c_1 \exp(x - x_j)$$

and data points d_Q were also assumed, $c = 1$ and $c_1 = 0.96$.

Figure 4.1: Plot of exact and estimate emission sources at different points in space.

4.3 Sample pseudo code for \hat{K}

$$\hat{K} = \frac{K^0 + C_{\Gamma} W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - c \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - Q \right] \times \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt}{1 + C_{\Gamma} W_f \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} \times \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} dx dt} \quad (4.3.1)$$

Basing equation (4.3.1) above, the pseudo code for \hat{K} can be represented as below:

1. Start
2. Define Function $f_1(x, t) = [q_t(x, t) + \nabla \cdot u(x, t)q(x, t) - c \nabla \cdot q(x, t) - Q(x, t)] * \nabla^2 q(x, t)$
3. Define Function $f_2(x, t) = \nabla^2 q(x, t) * \nabla^2 q(x, t)$
4. Input K^0 , C_{Γ} , and W_f
5. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (L) and number of sub intervals (N) for x
6. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (T) and number of sub intervals (M) for t
7. Create arrays for t and x using their lower limits, upper limits and number of sub intervals respectively
8. To calculate for the double integral in the numerator in equation (4.3.1) the Trapezoidal rule can be used to give an output Result_1
9. To calculate for the double integral in the denominator in equation (4.3.1) the Trapezoidal rule can be used to give an output Result_2

10. Calculate $\hat{K} = (K^0 + C_\Gamma * W_f * \text{Result}_1) / (1 + C_\Gamma * W_f * \text{Result}_2)$
11. Stop

4.4 Sample pseudo code for \hat{c}

$$\hat{c} = \frac{c^0 + C_\gamma W_f \int_0^T \int_\Omega \left[\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} q + u \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} - K \frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial x^2} - Q \right] \times \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} dx dt}{1 + C_\gamma W_f \int_0^T \int_\Omega \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} \times \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} dx dt} \quad (4.4.1)$$

Basing equation (4.4.1) above, the pseudo code for \hat{c} can be represented as below:

1. Start
2. Define Function $f_1(x, t) = \left[q_t(x, t) + \nabla \cdot u(x, t)q(x, t) - K \nabla^2 q(x, t) - Q(x, t) \right] * \nabla \cdot q(x, t)$
3. Define Function $f_2(x, t) = \nabla q(x, t) * \nabla q(x, t)$
4. Input c^0 , C_γ , and W_f
5. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (L) and number of sub intervals (N) for x
6. Input lower limit (0), upper limit (T) and number of sub intervals (M) for t
7. Create arrays for t and x using their lower limits, upper limits and number of sub intervals respectively
8. To calculate for the double integral in the numerator of equation (3.4.26) the trapezoidal rule can be used to give an output Result_1
9. To calculate for the double integral in the denominator of equation (3.4.26) the trapezoidal rule can be used to give an output Result_2
10. Calculate $\hat{c} = (c^0 + C_\gamma * W_f * \text{Result}_1) / (1 + C_\gamma * W_f * \text{Result}_2)$
11. Stop

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study involved assimilation of $PM_{2.5}$ data into the Eulerian transport model using weak constraint 4DVAR in order to simulate the long-range regional transport of smoke. Here the Euler-Lagrange systems of equations that optimize for the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration, wind fields, emission source, decay coefficient due to rainfall or temperature, and the diffusivity constant were derived.

The Euler-Lagrange system that was obtained when optimizing for the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration was decoupled using the representer method and a pseudo code was formed. Optimal estimates for the emission source, decay coefficient, and diffusivity constant were also obtained and their pseudo also provided. A sample simulation for the emission source was got after implementing it's pseudo code .

It is rather challenging to obtain the optimal estimate for the dispersion by the ambient wind. This is because at the moment there is no clear way on how to decouple the Euler-Lagrange systems of equations that result when using the weak constraint 4DVAR for non-constant parameters. We, therefore, suggest future research on using the representer method to estimate the non-constant ambient wind.

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